

FITSLIM — A HERBAL-BASED WEIGHT LOSS PRODUCT**Joldasov.A.I.****Mukhanova.A.A.****Tayirova. D.B.****Maksudova S.A.**

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Uzbekistan, Tashkent, oybek 45

e-mail: jallayar050@gmail.com, tel: +99897-354-48-77

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17328505>

Relevance: In recent years, obesity has become a serious medical and social problem worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), overweight and obesity lead to the development of cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, fatty liver disease and many other metabolic diseases. In addition to traditional medicines, dietary products based on medicinal plants are gaining importance in the prevention and treatment of obesity.

FitSlim is an innovative sweetener based on natural plant extracts, which is pharmaceutically safe, has a beneficial effect on the body, and is also designed in a dietary form for consumers.

Propose of study: The main goals of developing FitSlim sweets are: To create a natural, safe and effective remedy against obesity and overweight;

To preserve the beneficial properties of medicinal plants in the composition of the dessert mass; To develop a new dietary product that supports a healthy lifestyle.

Methods and methodology: In the study, ginger powder, green tea extract, fenugreek powder, and flax seeds were selected from medicinal plants. It has been noted in scientific sources that these plants have an effective effect on reducing obesity. The raw materials were first dried and ground into a fine powder. Bioactive substances were isolated from the plants through the extraction method.

The resulting extract was added to the dessert mass and low-temperature drying technology was used. The finished product was prepared for storage in hygienic packaging.

This technological process allowed for the maximum preservation of biologically active substances - polyphenols, flavonoids, vitamins and minerals.

Results: According to the results of the study, FitSlim dessert has the following positive effects: Activates metabolism and stimulates faster breakdown of fats; Normalizes appetite, reduces excess calorie intake;

Has an antioxidant effect, protecting cells from oxidative stress; Improves blood circulation, strengthens overall health.

Studies have shown that using FitSlim dessert in combination with a healthy diet and physical activity provides more effective results in preventing obesity.

Conclusion: To conclusion, it can be said that as a result of FitSlim is an innovative sweetener based on medicinal plants, the main advantages of which are: naturalness, safety and effectiveness. It has the potential to prevent obesity and overweight problems, promote a healthy lifestyle, and be widely used as a new product in the pharmaceutical and food industries.